

DESCRIBING OVARIAN DEVELOPMENT IN GIRLS FROM BIRTH TO 9 MONTHS

Bakoyeva Feruza Maksudovna

Assistant teacher in the “Medical faculty” of Alfraganus University

Email: fbaqoyeva@gmail.com

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5903-3531

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10682501>

Abstract

The decline in exposure to maternal estrogen during birth triggers an increase in the production of gonadotropins and other reproductive hormones in infants, a phenomenon referred to as minipuberty. This transient activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis is accompanied by heightened folliculogenesis and ovarian growth in girls. The growth of ovaries and changes in other reproductive organs during infancy is a normal part of development and may impact long-term reproductive function. However, established normative ranges for ovarian growth in infancy have not been determined or explored in relation to adult reproductive function.

While ovarian size has been characterized from birth to menopause, most data is derived from older girls and adult women. Limited information on ovarian size in infants and young girls is available from a few small, primarily cross-sectional studies. This study utilizes a large longitudinal cohort to contribute valuable insights for establishing reference ranges for postnatal ovarian growth in healthy infants. These size standards serve as a basis for comparing and defining normal or pathological ovaries during infancy, potentially aiding in the early identification of reproductive disorders. In epidemiologic studies, this data may be crucial for pinpointing early life exposures that could negatively impact ovarian development, which might not otherwise become apparent until puberty or reproductive years.

The primary objective of this study is to delineate ovarian growth trajectories and follicle development during the initial 9 months of life in a substantial longitudinal cohort of healthy girls enrolled at birth for a study on infant feeding and reproductive development.

Keywords: infant, minipuberty, ovarian growth.

2. Methods

2.1. Study Design

The National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS) Infant Feeding and Early Development (IFED) Study was an observational investigation conducted from August 2020 to November 2023. Its aim was to evaluate longitudinal variations in reproductive hormone concentrations and reproductive organ volumes during infancy relative to feeding methods, including breast milk, cow-milk formula, or soy formula. Detailed procedures for the study have been previously documented. Briefly, women were recruited from their third trimester of pregnancy until 72 hours after childbirth at eight regional hospitals in Philadelphia. Those indicating their intention to exclusively feed their child soy formula, cow-milk formula, or breast milk and consenting to formal screening were contacted by study personnel. Of the 524 mothers who consented to screening, 410 (78%) agreed to participate, with 399 (76% of those screened) completing the baseline visit (194 with baby girls). Exclusion criteria comprised being under 18 years of age, having a diagnosis of diabetes, thyroid disease, or other endocrine disorders (including polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS)), and taking specific

medications such as steroids, immunosuppressants, or pregnancy-maintaining hormones (including in vitro fertilization). Infant feeding history was assessed at each visit, and ongoing participation necessitated adherence to the selected feeding regimen (breast milk, cow-milk formula, soy formula), with allowances for supplementary food up to 15% of calories (at 13 weeks) and 20% (at 25 weeks) as infants aged.

2.2. Study Population

Infants were deemed eligible if they were singletons, born at term (37–42 weeks gestation), and had a birthweight between 2500 and 4500 grams. Gestational age was extracted from the mother's medical records, and birthweight requirements were confirmed from the infant's chart. Infants were excluded if they presented: 1) a major congenital malformation, 2) a chromosomal anomaly, 3) a significant illness affecting growth and development, 4) respiratory distress necessitating oxygen for over 4 hours, or 5) a blood-related sibling already enrolled in the study.

2.3. Outcome Measures

Upon enrollment, girls underwent their initial study visit within 72 hours of birth, followed by subsequent visits at 2, 4, 8, 12, 16, 20, 24, 28, 32, and 36 weeks. Trans-abdominal ultrasounds were conducted at the newborn visit (within 72 hours of birth) and subsequently at 4, 16, 24, and 32 weeks. Additionally, a subset of girls had an extra ultrasound at the 8-week visit. Research-protocol-trained sonographers utilized curved-array and linear-array transducers to image the ovaries. Three to four images were captured of the largest diameter of each ovary in the sagittal, transverse, and anterior-posterior planes. Dimension-specific diameters were calculated using the geometric mean of the replicated axis measurements. Ovarian volume was determined using the ellipsoid formula: $(\pi/6) \times L \times W \times D$. Ovarian volume at each visit was computed as the geometric mean of both ovaries when measurable. When only one ovary was visible and measurable, its volume was used for that visit. For girls with discernible ovaries, ovarian follicles were also documented. The count of visible growing follicles (antral follicle count) was categorized as none, 1 to 3, or >3 follicles for each ovary, and the diameter of the largest follicle on each ovary was recorded. Values for these ovarian follicle characteristics were reported from the ovary with the most follicles (for antral follicle count) or the largest measured follicle (for diameter).

3. Results

Out of the 44 mother-infant girl pairs enrolled in this study, seven infants lacked ovarian volume measurements, and twenty-four infants had ovarian volume measured at only one study visit, resulting in an analytical sample size of 32. Infant and maternal characteristics are detailed in Table 1. The participating infants were comprised of 19% black and 70% white, with a median gestational age of 39 weeks and a median neonatal weight of 3100 grams (IQR: 2870, 3440). Mothers had a median age of 26 years (IQR: 22, 29) at the time of their child's birth, and their infants underwent a median of five ultrasounds during the study period (range: 2 to 6). Among infants with visible ovaries, the percentage with both ovaries visualized ranged from 73% at the newborn visit to 93% at the 24-week visit.

In the complete cohort, the median ovarian volume was smallest during the newborn visit (median = 0.2 cm³, IQR: 0.1, 0.3) and reached its peak at the 16-week visit (median = 0.9 cm³, IQR: 0.6, 1.2). Notably, there was considerable variability in ovarian volume within study visits, particularly evident at the newborn visit and in the initial weeks of observation when

ovarian growth was more rapid. At the 4-week visit, the range of ovarian volume spanned from less than 0.1 cm³ to 4.9 cm³, which gradually narrowed to 0.1–2.3 cm³ by the 32-week visit. The diameter of the largest observable ovarian follicle was 0.2 cm at the newborn visit, increased to 0.8 cm at the 4-week visit, and then remained relatively stable across subsequent study visits. Among girls with discernible ovaries, 56% had at least one visible antral follicle during the newborn visit. This proportion escalated to between 90% and 100% between weeks 4 and 32, albeit the proportion of girls with more than three visible follicles on at least one ovary declined by the 32-week visit.

4. Interpretation

The initial growth of the ovary likely mirrors a response to the gonadotropin surge characteristic of minipuberty. Our findings suggest that ovarian growth during infancy is influenced by the number and size of developing follicles. It's conceivable that girls exhibiting visible follicles at birth may experience a more pronounced response to the hormonal shifts of minipuberty. While there was notable variability in ovarian volumes among girls of the same age, individual ovary size tended to remain consistent over time relative to the rest of the cohort (e.g., girls with large ovaries at 16 weeks also tended to have large ovaries at 32 weeks). The implications of large ovaries during infancy remain uncertain, but it's noteworthy that reproductive-aged women with certain gynecologic conditions like PCOS often exhibit larger ovarian volumes compared to those without PCOS. This raises the possibility that ovarian size in early life may also bear relevance to adult reproductive function.

Comparisons with other studies focusing on infant ovarian volume are limited. Most existing studies, such as those by Haber et al., Cohen et al., and Orbak et al., either lacked longitudinal assessments or had wide age intervals and small sample sizes, potentially contributing to variations in ovarian volume estimates compared to our study. Additionally, advancements in ultrasound technology over the past decades may have improved the precision of measurement compared to earlier studies. Our pilot study, the only one with longitudinal measures across infancy, reported a pattern of increasing ovarian volume after birth followed by a subsequent decrease during the 6–12 monthage period, akin to our observations in the IFED study. Notably, no previous study evaluated differences in ovarian growth based on the presence of newborn follicles, as we did in our investigation.

Regarding soy formula use, it's a common practice in the U.S. that exposes infants to phytoestrogens, potentially affecting reproductive development. Our study aligns with previous findings, suggesting no significant differences in ovarian volumes between breast-fed and soy formula-fed girls in the early weeks of follow-up. However, we observed a divergence in ovarian volume trajectory between soy formula-fed and breast milk-fed girls in later weeks of follow-up (after 4 months). Notably, this trajectory difference was not observed between cow-milk formula-fed and breast-fed girls. Nonetheless, findings at age 5 suggest that differences in ovarian volume trajectory observed in late infancy between breast-fed and soy formula-fed girls may not persist.

5. Conclusions

This study offers valuable data that can contribute to the development of reference standards for ovarian growth throughout infancy. Our findings indicate a surge in infant ovarian volume shortly after birth, potentially influenced by the number and size of developing follicles. Further investigation is necessary to elucidate the factors regulating ovarian growth and the

significance of infant follicle development during minipuberty, as these changes may serve as early indicators of future reproductive health.

References:

1. Chellakooty M, Schmidt IM, Haavisto AM, Boisen KA, Damgaard IN, Mau C, et al. Inhibin A, inhibin B, follicle-stimulating hormone, luteinizing hormone, estradiol, and sex hormone-binding globulin levels in 473 healthy infant girls. *J ClinEndocrinolMetab.* 2003; 88:3515–3520. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
2. Schmidt H, Schwarz H. Serum concentrations of LH and FSH in the healthy newborn. *European journal of endocrinology.* 2000; 143:213–215. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
3. Kuri-Hanninen T, Sankilampi U, Dunkel L. Activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis in infancy: minipuberty. *Horm Res Paediatr.* 2014; 82:73–80. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
4. Lanciotti L, Cofini M, Leonardi A, Penta L, Esposito S. Up-To-Date Review About Minipuberty and Overview on Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Gonadal Axis Activation in Fetal and Neonatal Life. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne).* 2018; 9:410. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
5. Francois CM, Petit F, Giton F, Gougeon A, Ravel C, Magre S, et al. A novel action of follicle-stimulating hormone in the ovary promotes estradiol production without inducing excessive follicular growth before puberty. *Sci Rep.* 2017; 7:46222. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
6. Nguyen RH, Umbach DM, Parad RB, Stroehla B, Rogan WJ, Estroff JA. US assessment of estrogen-responsive organ growth among healthy term infants: piloting methods for assessing estrogenic activity. *PediatrRadiol.* 2011; 41:633–642. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
7. Kelsey TW, Dodwell SK, Wilkinson AG, Greve T, Andersen CY, Anderson RA, et al. Ovarian volume throughout life: a validated normative model. *PLoS One.* 2013; 8:e71465. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
8. Griffin IJ, Cole TJ, Duncan KA, Hollman AS, Donaldson MD. Pelvic ultrasound measurements in normal girls. *ActaPaediatr.* 1995; 84:536–543. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
9. Cohen HL, Tice HM, Mandel FS. Ovarian volumes measured by US: bigger than we think. *Radiology.* 1990; 177:189–192. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
10. Pavlik E, DePriest P, Gallion H, Ueland F, Reedy M, Kryscio R, et al. Ovarian volume related to age. *Gynecologic oncology.* 2000; 77:410–412. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
11. Merz E, Miric-Tesanic D, Bahlmann F, Weber G, Wellek S. Sonographic size of uterus and ovaries in pre- and postmenopausal women. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol.* 1996; 7:38–42. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
12. Cohen HL, Shapiro MA, Mandel FS, Shapiro ML. Normal ovaries in neonates and infants: a sonographic study of 77 patients 1 day to 24 months old. *AJR Am J Roentgenol.* 1993; 160:583–586. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
13. кизи Наркулова, И. Р. (2022). ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КУРСАНТОВ-БИЛНГВОВ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ИНФОРМАЦИОННО-КОММУНИКАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 1(3), 185-193

14. Orbak Z, Kantarci M, Yildirim ZK, Karaca L, Doneray H. Ovarian volume and uterine length in neonatal girls. *J PediatrEndocrinolMetab.* 2007; 20:397–403. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
15. Haber HP, Mayer EI. Ultrasound evaluation of uterine and ovarian size from birth to puberty. *PediatrRadiol.* 1994; 24:11–13. [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]
16. Adgent MA, Umbach DM, Zemel BS, Kelly A, Schall JI, Ford EG, et al. A Longitudinal Study of Estrogen-Responsive Tissues and Hormone Concentrations in Infants Fed Soy Formula. *J ClinEndocrinolMetab.* 2018; 103:1899–1909. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Google Scholar](#)]